

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL:

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RETHINKING WATER SCARCITY INDICATORS TO IMPROVE SDG 6.4.2 MONITORING IN ALGERIA

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S1. Data collection protocol:

The data collection protocol is based on a structured integration of national planning datasets of the ministry in charge of Water¹ and water institutions, sectoral studies, and recent institutional updates.

The core dataset originates from the National Water Plan (PNE), which is composed of sector-specific reports covering: surface water resources (PNE 2010f, 2010c), groundwater resources (PNE 2010e), agricultural water demand (PNE 2010a), industrial water demand (PNE 2010b), and non-conventional water resources (PNE 2010d). Each component includes its own database, which was accessed and compiled to reconstruct a consistent national water balance framework, building on prior academic consolidation of these datasets (Kherbache 2014, 2020).

To ensure robustness, groundwater resource estimates were cross-validated using major hydrogeological studies conducted in Algeria, including (ENERGOPROJEKT/ANRH 2009b, 2009a) and (SOGREAH/ANRH 2010b, 2010a). These sources were used to refine estimates of aquifer potential and to support the definition of groundwater exploitation assumptions. The dataset was further updated using the revised National Water Plan (PNE 2018, 2019b, 2019a, 2019c), which provides more recent estimates at both national and regional scales. Additional updates for the period 2021–2024 were

¹ The Ministry of Water Resources (MRE) from 1999 to 2015. Since then, the sector has undergone multiple reforms: the Ministry of Water Resources and Environment (MREE) in May 2015; the Ministry of Water Resources and Water Security (MRESH) in July 2022; the Ministry of Public Works, Hydraulics, and Basic Infrastructure (MTPHIB) in September 2022; and the Ministry of Hydraulics since March 2023.

obtained through institutional data collection within recent FAO-supported projects (WEPS-NENA and IMI-SDGs), involving collaboration with national water sector agencies. When multiple datasets were available, priority was given to national planning databases (PNE), validated hydrogeological studies (ANRH-based), and international datasets (FAO, World Bank, UNDP) for consistency checks. This hierarchical selection ensured coherence across variables while explicitly acknowledging remaining uncertainties between sources (for this issue the readers can refer to Kherbache and Molle (2025)). These elements are systematically summarized in Table S1, which provides a structured overview of variables, data sources, processing rules, assumptions, and associated uncertainties used in the analysis.

Table S1. data sources, assumptions, and uncertainties

Category	Variable	Unit	Source	Years	Processing	Uncertainty	Used in
Water Resources	Total Renewable Water Resources (TRWRs)	Bm ³ /year	PNE 2010/PNE 2018/FAO	2010–2022	PNE/PDAREs databases; cross-checked with FAO	Moderate	WSI, exploitation index, SWSI
	Weak (Sustainable withdrawals)		SASS/ANRH	Up to 2030	Conservative	Hydro constraints	WSI
Groundwater assumption	Strong (Maximum withdrawals)		PNE/SASS	Up to 2030	Policy-driven	Non-sustainable	WSI
Population	Population	Million	ONS/PNE Algerian Water Company (ADE)/Ministry in charge of Water (MH)	2012 à 2030	Projection	Moderate	WSI
Withdrawals	Drinking water supply	Bm ³ /year		2021	PNE/PDAREs databases and water institutions	Good	Use-to-resource ratio, exploitation index
	Large-scale industry		ADE/MH	2021	PNE/PDAREs databases, and water institutions	Good	
	Irrigated agriculture		AGIRE, ONID, ANRH	2021	PNE/PDAREs databases, and water institutions	Low (illegal pumping)	

Source: authors

S2. Current state of water resource availability

In Algeria, surface water is perceived as dependent on precipitation and highly vulnerable to drought. In contrast, groundwater in the south, particularly in the northern Sahara, is often regarded as a reserve to address shortages on high plateaus. This section evaluates the validity of this assumption by presenting estimates of Algeria's water resource by hydrographic region (Fig. S1).

Fig. S1. Division and hydrographic regions of Algeria.

Source: Authors

S2.1. Impacts of climate change and drought in Algeria

Climate change has already significantly impacted the global water cycle. The 2023 IPCC report states that human activities, primarily greenhouse gas emissions, have clearly caused global warming, resulting in a 1.1°C increase in surface temperatures between 2011 and 2020 compared with 1850–1900. Emissions continue to rise due to unsustainable energy and land-use practices (IPCC 2023). In the Maghreb region, warming is estimated at over 1°C, with a pronounced trend over the past thirty years. Projections indicate an overall regional temperature increase of 2–4°C during the 21st century (Arrus 1997; PNUD 2009). Algeria is no exception to this global trend, with ten-year average temperatures in the west of the country (the Oran region) rising by approximately 1–1.8°C between

1971 and 2017 (Zeroual et al. 2017; Kherbache and Molle 2023). Global warming thus exacerbates water vulnerability in Algeria. It affects the environment, increases irrigation demands through higher evapotranspiration, reduces rainfall, leading to lower dam inflows, and diminishes groundwater recharge. Additionally, climate change threatens the sustainability of wetlands designated as Ramsar sites (50 sites in Algeria) (Ghodbani and Amokrane 2013; ABHO 2016; Kherbache and Molle, 2021, 2023).

Several public institutions, including the Ministry of Hydraulics (MH) and the National Water Resources Agency (ANRH), have launched projects to assess these impacts on water resources, the most recent being the update study of the National Water Plan (PNE). To measure supply deficits, the PNE (2010b) first calculated the average monthly supply over a 43-year period (1965–2008). The study's results highlighted the severity of deficits across several dam basins, organized by hydrographic region, during both average and dry periods. Supply deficits were found to decrease from west to east. The Oranie-Chott-Chergui (OCC) and Cheliff-Zahrez (CZ) regions were the most affected, with deficits ranging from 30% to 40%, particularly during 1991–2001 when dams were nearly dry and Algeria was preparing to import water. In the Constantinois-Seybouse-Mellegue (CSM) hydrographic region, drought was less severe, with deficits below 11%. Additional deficits of 26% for OCC, 17% for CZ, and 17% for Algérois Hodna Soummam (AHS) were reported² during the regional workshop for industrialists on “Preserving Water, the Source of Life and Sustainable Development: A Shared Commitment” held on June 29, 2025, in Blida, Algeria, by the head of the Hydrology Department at ANRH

S2.2. Surface water potential: rich eastern and poor western and Saharan regions

There are significant gaps in the statistical data in the literature concerning water issues in Algeria, as well as in the analytical documents published by the state institutions responsible for assessing the country's surface water potential. In fact, surface runoff during the colonial period was estimated at

² Without mentioning the period of analysis, which we assume to be the most recent.

15 Bm³ (19th International Geological Congress, Algiers 1952) (cited by Arrus (1985, p. 17). However, in 1987, the Ministry of Hydraulics estimated the total potential between 16 and 19 Bm³, of which 12.4 Bm³ was surface potential. In studies conducted by the ANRH covering the years of drought up to 1993, surface water was estimated at 12.4 Bm³ (CNES 2000). Currently, the (PNE 2010f) is estimated at 10.92 Bm³, which is distributed across the ABHs according to Fig. S2.

Source: Author from annex 2 of (PNE, 2010f).

Fig. S2. Regional differences between surface water inflows and the hydrographic region

The uneven distribution of precipitation results in a similarly unequal distribution of surface water. Although the OCC and CZ regions are more than three times larger than the CSM region in terms of area, they account for only 42% of surface water resources. The CSM region, which is the wettest, holds the largest share of surface water (45% of the national potential). The OCC and Sahara regions are the poorest, contributing to only 12% of the national total. The assessment of surface water potential reveals inconsistencies between data sources. This raises the question of whether there is a real decline due to climate change or whether there is a lack of knowledge.

S2.3. Groundwater availability: The assumption of inexhaustibility is fallible

S2.3.1. Groundwater in northern Algeria

While the MRE estimated northern Algeria's groundwater reserves at 2 Bm³ in 2005 and 2007, CNES (2000), based on ANRH studies, reported a similar value of 1.9 Bm³, and the PNE from 1993 and 2006 estimated northern groundwater at approximately 1.904 Bm³ and 2.11 Bm³, respectively.

Currently, the inventory provided by the National Water Plan (PNE 2010e, 2011) is considered the most reliable because of the level of detail in its assessment. Among the 177 aquifers in northern Algeria, 17 aquifers have been modeled, 31 have detailed quantification studies, and the resources of 130 aquifers have been determined through the rainfall/infiltration method (representing a resource of approximately 990 Mm³/year). The exploitable volume of these aquifers is estimated at 2.623 Bm³ for an average year and 0.714 Bm³ for a dry year (Table S2). The limited groundwater in the OCC and CZ regions complicates a precarious surface water situation. This is why meeting demand requires the exploitation of unconventional water sources (desalination and treated wastewater reuse).

Table S2. Spatial availability of groundwater in northern Algeria

Hydrographic regions	Surface water potential, average year		Surface water potential in dry years Mm ³
	Groundwater water Mm ³	Share of national resources	
OCC	547	21	87
CZ	346	13.1	87
AHS	1,063	40.5	327
CSM	667	25.4	213
Total	2,623	100%	714

Source: based on PNE (2010a) and annexes

S2.3.2. Groundwater of southern Algeria

The Algerian Sahara is characterized by groundwater resources from the Terminal Complex (CT) and Continental Intercalary (CI) aquifers, both of which formed during rainy periods more than 400,000 years ago. According to the MRE data, the water stored in these aquifers is approximately 60,000 Bm³, and 40,000 Bm³ which are located in Algeria and span an area of approximately 700,000 km². For the CT aquifer, exploitation requires deep pumping at depths of 100–400 m, whereas the CI aquifer,

known as the “Albian”, lies at 1,000–1,500 m. These resources are fossil, fragile, and nonrenewable (or minimally renewable), receiving 870 Mm³/year (PNE 2010e). This inflow is negligible compared with the volumes extracted by countries sharing these aquifers, which are exploited like mines, leading to depletion. Consequently, the exploitable volumes of these aquifers remain low (Table S3).

Table S3. Assessment of exploitable volumes for CI and CT

Aquifers	Weak assumption (2050) (Mm³/year)	Strong assumption (2050) (Mm³/year)
<i>Continental Intercalaire (CI)</i>	1210	4400
<i>Continental Terminal (CT)</i>	1120	1700
Total	2330	6100

Source: PNE(2010d, p. 103)

The World Bank (2023, p.67) estimates that approximately 1,280 Bm³ of exploitable reserves are available in the transboundary aquifer system shared by Algeria, Tunisia, and Libya, which could theoretically sustain withdrawals of about 2.7 Bm³/year over 475 years. The CI and CT aquifers are currently exploited through South–South water transfer (In Salah–Tamanrasset) and are planned for mobilization in South–North (South–High Plateaus) transfer projects. The additional volumes withdrawn from the aquifers are 63 Mm³/year and 524 Mm³/year, respectively. Beyond these resources, PNE (2010d) identified 29 hydrogeological units in the far south, with an estimated 257.4 Mm³/year, whereas resources in Chott Melghir are estimated at 109 Mm³/year (Table S4).

Table S4. Total of groundwater in Algeria

Average annual potential Regions	Groundwater in Mm³	Share (%) (Weak assumption)	Share (%) (Strong assumption)
Groundwater in northern Algeria (1)	2623	49.3	28.9
Chott Melghir (north)	109	2.1	1.2
<i>Continental intercalaire (CI)</i> ^a	1210 (4400)	22.7	48.4
Complexe terminal (CT)	1120 (1700)	21	18.7
Groundwater in the Extreme South	257.4	4.8	2.8
Total of groundwater in the South (2)	2696.4 (6466.4)	50.7	71.1
Total of groundwater (1) + (2)	5319.4 (9089.4)	100%	100%

^aIn brackets, this is the strong assumption about the fossil waters of the South according to table S3

Source: Author from PNE (2010d) and annexes

Notably, excessive groundwater exploitation is unsustainable. Algeria envisages using these resources as a safety valve and to support development in the High Plateaus and southern regions, specifically the agricultural sector, through irrigation expansion in the context of limited surface water and no desalination alternatives (MREE 2017; MRE/MADRP 2017; Services du Premier Ministre 2020; El-Mouradia 2024). However, it is essential to consider the transfer costs in these projects. For example, the CT aquifer contains very saline water, and the CI aquifer has high temperatures (50°C). Mobilization costs include pumping costs that increase gradually as groundwater levels drop and desalination and/or cooling costs, given that the water requires demineralization and/or cooling.

S2.3.3. Summary and general assessment of Algeria's water resources

Based on the above analysis, the overall water resources of Algeria are summarized in Table S5. Therefore, Algeria's total water resources are estimated at 16.24 Bm³/year in the case of the weak assumption of groundwater in the south and 20 Bm³/year in the case of the strong assumption (Table S5). This assessment of PNE does not differ significantly from those cited recently. Thus, according to reports and planning documents, the water resources available at the national level vary: 19.2 Bm³/y (Cour des comptes 2019), 18 Bm³/year (MRE 2020; Sonatrach/ME/MTEER 2021), 19.9 Bm³/year (MRE 2019), and 19.4 Bm³/year (MREE 2017). These figures are comparable to earlier estimates of 19.12 Bm³/year (Pérennès 1993) and 20 Bm³/year (CNES 2003). Historical estimates reported 18 Bm³/year in 1952 (Arrus 1985) and 16–19 Bm³/year in 1987 (Arrus 2003) and between 16 and 19 Bm³/y in 1987. The FAO gives low estimates for 2022, with a total renewable water of 11.67 Bm³, including 1.52 Bm³ of renewable groundwater (from AQUASTAT: <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en>).

Table S5. Global assessment of Algeria's water resources (Mm³)

Hydrographic region	Surface water	Groundwater	Total by region
OCC	702	547	1249
CZ	1340	346	1686
ASH	3359	1063	4422
CSM	4908	667	5575
Sahara	611.6	2696.4 (6466,4)	3308 (7078)

Total	10,920.6	5319.4 (9089.4)	16,240 (20,010)
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Source: author.

Discrepancies and gaps between FAO estimates and national data stem from the FAO's conservative focus on renewable flows and the systematic deduction of Environmental Flow Requirements (EFR) (see FAO (2024)). As highlighted in Kherbache and Molle (2025), while national sources often include exploitable fossil groundwater, the FAO's standardized methodology prioritizes long-term hydrological sustainability, leading to lower reported availability.

S2.3.4. Regional disparities in water availability

To further quantify regional disparities and their evolution over time, Table S6 presents water availability per capita by hydrographic region for 2012, 2024, and 2030, based on population dynamics and total water resource estimates under weak and strong groundwater assumptions. These results are utilized to produce Fig.3 in the main manuscript.

Table S6. Evolution of water availability by hydrographic region in Algeria

hydrographic region	Total water resources Mm ³	Population (2012) ^a	Population (2024) ^b	Population (2030) ^b	m ³ /capita. (2012)	m ³ /capita. (2024)	m ³ /capita. (2030)
OCC	1249	5.3	6.58	7.44	236	190	168
CZ	1686	5.7	7.07	8.00	296	238	211
ASH	4422	11.9	14.77	16.71	372	299	265
CSM	5575	8.5	10.55	11.93	656	529	467
Sahara	3308 (7078)	5.7	7.07	8.00	580/1242	468/1001	413/885
Total	16,240/20,010	37.1	46.7	52.08	438/539	348/428	312/384

^aFor 2012, the population distribution (in millions) by hydrographic region.

^bThe population estimates (in millions) for 2030 are based on the National Water Plan (updated 2018), as well as projections for 2024. The distribution of the population across hydrographic regions for 2024 and 2030 is derived from the 2018 PNE database.

^cValues are presented as weak / strong groundwater assumptions.

Source: Author's estimates.

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